

Schedule		8:00 a.m.	11:00 p.m.	2:00 p.m.	5:00 p.m.	8:00 p.m.
Food Group	No. SFS/d	Breakfast No. SFS/d	Snack 1 No. SFS/d	Lunch No. SFS/d	Snack 2 No. SFS/d	Dinner No. SFS/d
1. Vegetables	3	0	0	2	0	1
2. Fruits	6	2	1	2	1	0
3. Cereals						
A) Non-fat	3	0	0	2	0	1
B) With fat	2	2	0	0	0	0
4. Legumes	1	0	0	1	0	0
5. Animal Origin (AO)						
A) Very low fat	1	0	0	0	0	1
B) Low fat	2	0	0	2	0	0
C) Moderate fat	0	0	0	0	0	0
D) High fat	0	0	0	0	0	0
6. Milk						
A) Low fat	0	0	0	0	0	0
B) Reduced fat	0	0	0	0	0	0
C) Whole	0	0	0	0	0	0
D) With sugar	0	0	0	0	0	0
7. Fats						
A) Without protein	4	1	0	2	0	1
B) With protein	2	0	1	0	1	0
8. Sugars						
A) Non-fat	3.5	1.5	1	1	0	0
B) With fat	0	0	0	0	0	0

i.e. same individual example as in Table 1. Standard food servings (SFS) according to the Mexican food equivalent exchange lists (SMAE) [27].